

Evaluation of Requirements Cluster

Dear participant, in the following form you must judge each requirement in each cluster of requirements inferred by ReqCluster4IoT. You must consider the cluster as a whole and judge whether that specific requirement is consistent with its cluster.

You must also judge whether the IoT feature found for that cluster is adequate. At the end of each judgment there will be an open text field, in which the user is advised to give more details about the reasons for their choices.

[Switch account](#)

* Indicates required question

Email *

Record
response

as the email to be included with my

Name: *

Your answer

Cluster 1:

*

Characteristic: "Services"

Is part of the cluster

Is not part of the cluster

I don't know

"The system shall allow users to create accounts and log in using secure authentication methods. Users should be able to assign different access levels (e.g., admin, guest) to various members of the household."

"The application shall enable users to remotely control connected devices from anywhere through the internet. Users should be able to turn devices on or off, adjust settings, or activate/deactivate automation rules."

"The application should use encryption to protect data transmitted between the smart devices and the cloud, ensuring the privacy and security of user data. It should also detect and alert users about suspicious activities (e.g., unauthorized access attempts)."

"The system should support multiple user profiles with different permissions, allowing for personalized

automation settings for different members of the household."

"The system shall allow users to back up their automation rules, device configurations, and user settings. It should also provide a way to restore this data in case of data loss or migration to a new device."

"The application should notify users about available firmware updates for connected devices and allow them to install updates through the interface. It should also support automatic updates for the application itself."

Comments about cluster 1

Your answer

Cluster 2:

*

Characteristic: "Things"

Is part of the cluster

Is not part of the cluster

I don't know

"The application should support integration with a wide range of smart home devices, including but not limited to smart lights, thermostats, security cameras, door locks, and appliances. It should provide an easy way for users to connect and configure new devices."

"The application should provide both mobile and web interfaces that are responsive and user-friendly, allowing users to control smart home devices from any device with internet access."

"The system shall provide geofencing features that allow automation to be triggered based on the location of the user's smartphone (e.g., turning on the lights when arriving home)."

Comments about cluster 2

Your answer

Cluster 3: *

Characteristic: "Data"

Is part of the cluster

Is not part of the cluster

I don't know

"The system shall provide real-time monitoring of all connected smart devices, allowing users to view the current status and settings (e.g., whether lights are on, thermostat temperature, door lock status)."

"The system shall allow users to create custom automation rules that define how devices should behave based on specific conditions or events (e.g., turning on lights when motion is detected or lowering the thermostat at a set time). Users should be able to combine multiple conditions and actions in their automation scripts."

"The application should be able to connect with third-party services, such as weather forecasting services to adjust heating/cooling based on outdoor temperatures or geolocation services for setting home/away modes."

"The application should collect and store data from all connected devices for historical analysis. Users should be able to visualize this data through charts or reports to understand patterns in device usage."

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Comments about cluster 3

Your answer

Cluster 4:

*

Characteristic: "Interaction"

	Is part of the cluster	Is not part of the cluster	I don't know
"The system shall support integration with popular voice assistants like Amazon Alexa, Google Assistant, and Apple Siri, allowing users to control devices through voice commands."	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
"The system shall send notifications to users about important events, such as security alerts, changes in the status of devices, or failures in automation routines. Notifications should be customizable to allow users to choose the events they want to be notified about."	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
"The system shall provide features for monitoring energy usage of connected devices and suggest optimization strategies for reducing power consumption. Users should be able to view historical energy consumption data."	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
"The system should implement fail-safe mechanisms to	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

handle situations where connectivity is lost, such as retaining the last known device state or automatically switching to a default state."

"The application should include a feedback mechanism for users to report bugs, suggest improvements, and access help resources. A support channel should be available for troubleshooting common issues."

"The system shall support various communication protocols (e.g., Wi-Fi, Zigbee, Z-Wave, Bluetooth) to ensure compatibility with a wide range of IoT devices."

Comments about cluster 4

Your answer

Cluster 5: *
Characteristic: "Action"

Is part of the cluster

Is not part of the cluster

I don't know

"The application shall allow users to set schedules for connected devices (e.g., setting the lights to turn on at sunset or the thermostat to adjust temperature based on a daily routine)."

Comments about cluster 5

Your answer

Next

Clear form

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